

Molecular interaction studies of caffeine in aqueous metal chloride solutions at 308.15 K

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Abstract : Ultrasonic speed (u), density (d) and viscosity (η) of caffeine in aqueous solutions of potassium chloride, sodium chloride, magnesium chloride and calcium chloride have been measured at 308.15 K. From these data, thermodynamic interaction coefficient, isentropic compressibility (β_s), intermolecular free length (L_f), apparent molar volume (ϕ_v), relative association (R_A) and acoustic impedance (Z) have been computed. All the derived parameters are correlated with the molar composition of solutions. Depending on the molecular interactions and the nature of the solutions show the change in structure of solvent when solute is added to it. The viscosity coefficients A and B of Jones-Dole equation have been determined and employed to throw light on the mechanism of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Keywords : Molecular interaction, caffeine, viscosity, ultrasonics.

Ultrasonic velocity, density, viscosity and related properties provide an interesting information about solute-solute, solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions in aqueous solution¹. Ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions of bio-molecule and its derivatives in the presence of metal ions are very important in understanding the nature of bio-active molecule in the body system². In view of the above importance, an attempt has been made to study the density, ultrasonic velocity and viscosity of metal chlorides in binary aqueous solution of caffeine (1,3,7-trimethyl-xanthine), which is a purine base found in most body tissue fluids and their derivatives are used in medicine for their bronchodilator effects³.

Results and discussion

Experimentally measured densities (d) and ultrasonic speeds (u) of caffeine in aqueous solutions of NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂ and CaCl₂ at 308.15 K are presented in Table 1. Ultrasonic speed (u), density (d) data were employed to obtain adiabatic compressibility (β_s), acoustic impedance (Z), relative association (R_A) and intermolecular free length (L_f) of solutions using following relations

$$\beta_s = 1/u^2d, Z = ud, R_A = Vu^{1/3}, L_f = K\beta_s^{1/2}$$

where K is Jacobson constant, which is temperature dependent and V is molar volume.

The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) and apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) were computed as below :

Table 1. Values of density (d), ultrasonic speed (u) and relative viscosity (η) of caffeine in aqueous potassium chloride, sodium chloride, magnesium chloride and calcium chloride at 308.15 K

C (mol/kg)	CaCl ₂			MgCl ₂			KCl			NaCl		
	$d \times 10^{-3}$ (kg/m ³)	u (m/s)	$\eta_r \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$d \times 10^{-3}$ (kg/m ³)	u (m/s)	$\eta_r \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$d \times 10^{-3}$ (kg/m ³)	u (m/s)	$\eta_r \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	$d \times 10^{-3}$ (kg/m ³)	u (m/s)	$\eta_r \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
0.0000	0.9964	1496.00	0.6825	0.9969	1495.20	0.7184	0.9960	1535.6	0.6889	0.9973	1535.38	0.7376
0.0100	0.9966	1515.20	0.7179	0.9974	1507.44	0.7323	0.9965	1522.9	0.7323	0.9979	1519.20	0.7521
0.0201	0.9968	1522.40	0.7116	0.9992	1513.06	0.7375	0.9971	1530.1	0.7147	0.9987	1529.60	0.7490
0.0403	0.9986	1531.60	0.7034	0.9998	1533.80	0.7524	0.9980	1537.1	0.7090	0.9994	1541.60	0.7424
0.0606	0.9989	1540.00	0.6939	1.0009	1554.00	0.7693	0.9994	1542.4	0.7071	1.0002	1567.20	0.7398
0.0812	1.0004	1545.60	0.6917	1.0015	1562.08	0.7843	1.0007	1550.0	0.7041	1.0018	1572.80	0.7394

$$\phi_v = 1000 (d_0 - d_s)md_0d_s + (M/d_s),$$

$$\phi_k = 1000 (\beta_s - \beta_0)/d_0 + \phi_v\beta_s$$

where d_0 and d_s are the densities of solvent and solution respectively, m is the molality of the solution and M is the molar mass of solute. β_0 and β_s are adiabatic compressibilities of the solvent and solution respectively.

The values of β_s , Z , R_A , L_f , ϕ_v and ϕ_k obtained in the present investigation are presented in Table 2.

The variation of apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) and apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) with the square root of its concentration can be adequately represented by the Masson equation,

$$Y = Y^0 + S_v c^{1/2}$$

where Y represents ϕ_v or ϕ_k , Y^0 is the value at infinite dilution and S_v and S_k are the experimental slope. The

values of ϕ_v^0 and ϕ_k^0 , S_v and S_k are reported in Table 3.

Viscosity data were analyzed in the light of Jones-Dole equation

$$\eta_r - 1/c^{1/2} = A + Bc^{1/2}$$

where A and B viscosity coefficients characteristics of solute-solute and solute-solvent interaction respectively. These coefficients were obtained from the intercept and slope of linear plots of $\eta_r - 1/c^{1/2}$ versus $c^{1/2}$. The values of A and B are given in Table 3.

The results of density (d) and ultrasonic speed (u) indicate association amongst the molecules and greater solute-solvent interaction, increase linearly with concentration of electrolyte⁴.

The pronounced increase or decrease in the values of these parameters with composition of solutions indicates the presence of interaction between the components

Table 2. Values of isentropic compressibility (β_s), acoustic impedance (Z), apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) and apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k), molecular association (R_A) and intermolecular free length (L_f) of caffeine with aqueous solutions of electrolyte KCl, NaCl, MgCl₂ and CaCl₂ at 308.15 K

Electrolytic	C (mol/kg)	$\beta_s \times 10^{-11}$ (m ² N ⁻¹)	$Z \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	L_f (Å)	$R_A \times 10^{-6}$	$\phi_v \times 10^{-6}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\phi_k \times 10^{-14}$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹ Pa)
KCl	0.0000	42.56	1531.97	0.3926			
	0.0100	43.41	1517.67	0.3094	1.00341	178.142	7.75
	0.0201	42.78	1525.04	0.3903	1.00127	173.425	2.21
	0.0404	42.39	1536.78	0.3918	1.00254	161.381	-2.69
	0.0606	42.10	1541.58	0.3903	1.00211	142.545	-1.57
	0.0812	41.57	1551.48	0.3880	1.00122	139.451	-0.62
NaCl	0.0000	42.54	1530.98	0.3925			
	0.0100	42.44	1515.09	0.3920	1.00423	184.707	9.89
	0.0201	42.34	1525.80	0.3939	1.00659	179.365	2.19
	0.0403	42.10	1540.70	0.3905	1.00085	143.765	-0.50
	0.0606	40.70	1567.51	0.3839	0.9852	141.252	-2.39
	0.0811	40.35	1572.29	0.3823	0.9799	136.828	-2.14
MgCl ₂	0.0000	44.86	1503.53	0.4091			
	0.0099	44.12	1511.97	0.4031	0.9984	144.942	-6.93
	0.0200	43.71	1533.58	0.3997	0.9973	136.353	-5.43
	0.0403	42.51	1555.39	0.3979	0.9944	129.46	-5.42
	0.0606	41.37	1562.23	0.3871	0.9923	128.252	-5.31
	0.0811	40.91	1490.59	0.3849	0.9901	121.031	-4.30
CaCl ₂	0.0000	44.84	1490.72	0.4030			
	0.0099	43.70	1510.06	0.3978	0.9958	180.376	-1.09
	0.0201	43.58	1517.52	0.3959	0.9949	179.308	-6.96
	0.0403	42.68	1529.41	0.3932	0.9943	153.899	-4.74
	0.0607	42.21	1538.33	0.3910	0.9936	144.449	-3.68
	0.0812	41.84	1546.35	0.3893	0.9931	140.435	-3.08

molecules in the system⁵. The linear increase in ultrasonic speed (u), specific impedance (Z) and decrease in isentropic compressibility (β_s) with increase in concentration of electrolytes suggests solute-solvent interaction. However, decrease in isentropic compressibility (β_s) is due to structural promotion of solvent molecules. However, decrease in adiabatic compressibility (β_s) with increasing concentration of electrolyte is due to strong interaction of electrolyte with OH^- and CH_3 groups of caffeine and also due to presence of hydrogen bonding. This clearly suggests that strength of interaction of caffeine molecule increases with increase in concentration of the electrolyte⁶.

The positive values of (ϕ_v) indicate the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions. It is observed from the Table 2 that, the apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) decreases with increase in concentration of electrolyte, possibly due to increase in ionic concentration and the electrostriction effect⁷. This may be due to associative interaction amongst the caffeine molecule. The plots of ϕ_v against square root of concentration were found to be linear. The partial molar volume (ϕ_v^0) caffeine-metal chloride system has been obtained by fitting (ϕ_v) values in the Masson equation using least square method and are given in Table 3. The values of (ϕ_v^0) are positive, indicating greater solute-solute interaction⁸.

The structural changes are more susceptible to viscosity as compared to temperature, pressure and dielectric constant of the medium. Viscosity data were analyzed in the light of Jones-Dole equation. A perusal of Table 3, shows that the values of A coefficient are negative for all the concentrations of aqueous solution electrolytes, thereby showing the presence of weak ion-ion interaction. It is also evident from the data that the values of coefficient B are positive and fairly large for the four metal chlorides system studied at 308.15 K. This shows the presence of ion-solvent interaction and mutual comparison shows that the values of B coefficient (ion-solvent interaction) are in the order of $\text{NaCl} < \text{KCl} < \text{CaCl}_2 < \text{MgCl}_2$. The value of B coefficient is a measure of order or disorder introduced by the ions/electrolyte into solvent structure¹¹.

Experimental

Caffeine was procured from HiMedia Laboratory Ltd. (99.5% pure) and used after drying in desiccator for 24 h. Metal chlorides, NaCl , KCl , MgCl_2 , CaCl_2 were of A.R. grade. All the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water, degassed by boiling having specific conductance less than $0.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$. The densities were measured with precalibrated bicapillary pycnometer

Table 3. Values of partial molar volume (ϕ_v) and its experimental slope (S_v), partial molar compressibility (ϕ_k) and its experimental slope (S_k) and Jones-Dole coefficient A and B of caffeine with aqueous of electrolyte at 308.15 K

Electrolytic	C (mol/kg)	$\phi_v^0 \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}$)	$S_v \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ kg}$)	$\phi_k^0 \times 10^{-15}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ Pa}$)	$S_k \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1} \text{ kg}$)	A ($\text{kg}^{-1/2} \text{ mol}^{-1/2}$)	B ($\text{kg}^{-1/2} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
KCl	0.01	201.95	-220.44	9.7903	-0.0045	-3.402	8.9554
NaCl	0.01	212.47	-283.76	1.3264	-0.0061	-3.1925	8.8891
MgCl_2	0.01	207.85	-211.3	-7.6184	0.0011	-3.4675	10.134
CaCl_2	0.01	207.44	-245.13	-1.3693	0.0040	-3.5017	9.0819

Ultrasonic velocity in solution depends on intermolecular free length (L_p) according to the Eyring and Kincaid model⁹. It is also evident that, relative intermolecular free length has been found to decrease in concentration of all the systems. This indicates significant interaction between solute-solvent molecules¹⁰. The interaction, which may also attributed to the decrease in number of free ions, showing the occurrence of ionic dissociation due to ion-ion interaction. The relative association (R_A) depends on the ultrasonic velocity and density of the solvent and the solution, and is influenced by the structure breaking tendency of the solvent molecule on addition of solute.

and the accuracy in density measurement was of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ g/cm}^3$. Ultrasonic velocity was measured by a single crystal variable path interferometer (Mittal-Model-F-81) at 2 MHz. Viscosity measurements were performed with precalibrated Ostwald's type viscometer.

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